

Article

The Impact of Oil Production on Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation

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Abstract: *This paper investigates the impact of oil production on economic development and poverty alleviation from 1990 to 2022. As one of Africa's largest oil producers, Nigeria has witnessed significant economic changes due to its oil wealth; however, this has not translated into equitable growth or substantial poverty reduction. The study aims to analyze the effects of inflation rates, tariffs, and literacy rates on economic development and poverty alleviation. Analytical methods include the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, cointegration test and First Difference ARDL model. The study reveals that despite generating substantial oil revenues, over 40% of Nigerians live below the poverty line, underscoring the phenomenon of the "resource curse." Furthermore, it identifies gaps in policy effectiveness, local community engagement, and long-term economic sustainability. By analyzing the relationship between oil production and socio-economic outcomes, this paper calls for targeted policy interventions that prioritize equitable wealth distribution and sustainable development strategies to mitigate poverty in Nigeria. The study emphasizes the need for economic diversification and balanced sectoral development to optimize economic potential and enhance welfare in Nigeria.*

Keywords: *Economic Development; Inflation; Oil Production; Poverty Alleviation; Resource Curse; Tariffs*

1. Introduction

The biggest oil producer in Africa, Nigeria, poses a perplexing conundrum. The nation struggles with pervasive poverty, underdevelopment, and economic instability while having a plethora of natural resources (Heinberg, 2003). Many studies have examined the connection between Nigeria's economic growth and oil output, especially because the nation is one of Africa's biggest oil producers. The petroleum industry, which contributes considerably to Nigeria's GDP and export earnings, has influenced the country's economy ever since oil was discovered in Oloibiri in 1956 (OPEC, 2022). The paradox of poverty endures in spite of the wealth created by oil, which begs the question of whether oil profits are effective in promoting economic expansion and reducing poverty. It was anticipated that Nigeria would see fast economic growth and development following the discovery of oil. Rather, corruption, poor management, and boom-and-bust cycles have afflicted the nation's oil-rich economy (Deffeyes, 2001). Since the 1970s, Nigeria's economy has been centered on oil extraction, which provides 80% of government revenue and 90% of foreign exchange revenues (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2020). Over time, the oil sector's share of Nigeria's GDP has varied, reaching a high of 45% in 2000

before falling to 10% in 2020 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). The necessity to reevaluate the contribution of oil production to Nigeria's economic growth is highlighted by this instability. With almost 87 million people living below the poverty line, Nigeria's poverty rates are still startlingly high (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Despite economic expansion and rising oil income, the nation's poverty headcount ratio has obstinately remained the same (World Bank, 2022).

Nigeria faced severe socioeconomic difficulties and varying oil prices and production levels between 1990 and 2022. During this time, oil accounted for more than 80% of government revenue and contributed about 10% of Nigeria's GDP (World Bank, 2023). For the vast majority of Nigerians, however, the oil boom did not result in a fair distribution of income or appreciable increases in living conditions. Rather, problems like environmental degradation, poor management, and corruption have made the people's problems worse (Human Rights Watch, 2021). With more than 40% of its people living below the national poverty line, Nigeria has one of the highest rates of poverty in the world despite its substantial oil wealth (UNDP, 2022). This paradox poses significant queries about the ways in which oil production influences economic growth and the reduction of poverty. Whether or if oil riches results in real advantages for the populace depends on a number of factors, including governance, institutional quality, and public policy responses (Ibeanu, 2020). Numerous academics contend that Nigeria's economic progress has been impeded by the "resource curse," often known as the paradox of abundance. This phenomenon describes how nations with abundant natural resources typically see lower rates of economic growth and inferior development results than those with less abundant natural resources (Ross, 2015). Nigeria is more susceptible to shocks to the world oil price because of the increased corruption and lack of economic diversification brought about by the influx of oil revenue (Adeola & Evans, 2019). In addition to impeding other industries like manufacturing and agriculture, the dependence on oil earnings has made poverty and economic inequality worse (ITA, 2023).

The efficiency of Nigeria's economic development policies is seriously called into doubt by this discrepancy between economic growth and poverty alleviation. It is still unclear how Nigerian oil production, economic growth, and poverty reduction are related. Prior research has looked into the environmental effects of oil production (Akpojomare, 2016) or the macroeconomic effects of oil shocks (Iwayemi, 2014). However, more research is needed to determine the precise mechanisms by which oil production influences economic growth and the reduction of poverty. Therefore, the goals of this study are to: examine how oil production affects Nigeria's economic development; look into how oil production affects the reduction of poverty; and, finally, determine the factors that influence the relationship between oil production, economic development, and poverty alleviation. This research aims to contribute to the existing literature by providing a comprehensive understanding of the impact of oil production on economic development and poverty alleviation in Nigeria. The findings will inform policy recommendations for optimizing Nigeria's oil resources to achieve sustainable economic development and poverty reduction. The following research questions were aimed at being addressed in order to achieve this: What impact has Nigeria's oil output had on the country's economic growth between 1990 and 2022? In the same time frame, how much has Nigeria's oil output helped to reduce poverty? What are the main moderators of the relationship between economic progress, poverty reduction, and oil production? This article intends to analyze the impact of oil production on economic development and poverty alleviation in Nigeria from 1990 to 2022, revealing the multiple mechanisms at play. Although prior research has emphasized the negative consequences of oil dependence, there is still a lack of knowledge regarding the precise policy measures that could reduce poverty and promote long-term economic growth. Furthermore, further research is necessary to fully understand the impact of oil extraction on the ecosystem and the significance of community engagement.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Empirical Review

According to Baumeister and Kilian (2016), volatility in oil prices is an unanticipated component of a large change in the price of oil, which is defined as the difference between the realized and projected prices of oil. In other words, if the price of crude oil rises on the international market at the expense of domestic oil prices, it could stimulate economic growth. However, the total impact of changes in the price of crude oil on enterprises and economic growth is largely determined by how the government

manages its earnings, both past and present (Ighosewe et al., 2021). In the past, the majority of Nigeria's government revenue and foreign exchange profits have come from the production and export of crude oil. Accordingly, the performance of the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is greatly impacted by variations in crude oil output and pricing (Igbodika et al., 2016).

Bucur (2023) investigates the multifaceted nature of poverty, emphasizing its persistent presence as a global economic and social issue using qualitative content analysis. The reviewed study explores sustainable solutions for poverty alleviation, focusing on the integration of social and economic dimensions through sustainable development approaches. The body of empirical research corroborates the findings presented in the abstract, showcasing that sustainable solutions such as economic inclusion, infrastructure investment, and community-based strategies have significant social and economic impacts. Collectively, these approaches reinforce the argument that sustainable development is a viable pathway to poverty reduction.

In a study conducted by Bolarinwa (2023) on the effect of formal education on poverty reduction in Nigeria. The study adopted the OLS regression and unit root tests.

The findings from this study are consistent with a broader body of empirical research, affirming the pivotal role of formal education in poverty reduction. By improving educational funding efficiency, fostering education-business linkages, and emphasizing skills development, Nigeria can leverage education as a powerful tool for poverty alleviation.

Similarly, Ocolişanu et al. (2023) conducted an appraisal of the impact of the circular economy on sustainable economic growth making use of descriptive statistics especially graphs. In the course of the study, it was observed that while the circular economy holds promise for sustainable growth, empirical studies identify challenges, including high initial costs, technological gaps, and resistance to change. Moreover, the unequal distribution of benefits across economies and sectors necessitates tailored strategies to maximize circular economy's potential. According to the World Bank Report (2023), Nigeria's expected current account deficit will remain at an average of 0.3% of GDP from 2013 to 2025 due to declining prices and stalling oil production. Although oil prices averaged \$101 per barrel annually in 2022, Nigeria's oil GDP had a real rise of -19.2% by the end of the year. The nation's unstable situation was demonstrated by this decline in oil production (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). Nigeria's oil sector accounted for about 9% of the country's GDP before the Corona Pandemic. The oil sector contributed 5.9% of the total real GDP from October to December 2020, which was almost three percentage points less than its contribution from July to September of the same year (Sasu, 2023). A significant impact on Nigeria's economic success is the variation in the amount of crude oil produced. Nigeria ranks sixth globally and produces the most oil in Africa (World Bank, 2022; Olofinbiyi et al., 2021). Crude oil production has been significantly affected by pipeline vandalism, oil theft, and attacks on the Niger Delta's oil infrastructure, which has had a significant impact on the nation's GDP and decreased government revenue (Iwayemi et al., 2019).

2.2. Theoretical Review

Oil production has been a significant aspect in Nigeria's economic environment, influencing both economic development and poverty alleviation initiatives. This theoretical analysis investigates the relationship between oil production and these economic results by addressing numerous key ideas and models.

2.2.1. Peak oil theory

According to the peak oil theory, conventional crude oil sources have either reached or are on the verge of reaching their maximum production capacity globally as of the early 21st century and would see a sharp decline in volume by the middle of the century. "Conventional" oil sources are readily accessible

deposits created by conventional onshore and offshore wells. Oil is extracted from these wells using mechanical walking beam pumps, natural pressure, or well-known backup techniques like pumping gas or water into the well to force oil to the surface. The term "unconventional oil sources" refers to oil deposits that need significant labour and financial resources to extract, such as oil sands, oil shales, oil recovered from "tight rock" formations using hydraulic fracturing, and oil found in deep water wells located far offshore. Peak oil theory proponents do not always assert that conventional oil supplies will run out suddenly, leading to severe shortages and a worldwide energy crisis. Rather, the theory contends that crude oil prices will likely stay high and possibly even rise further over time as easily extractable oil production inevitably peaks and declines (even in previously abundant regions like Saudi Arabia). This is especially true if future global oil demand rises in tandem with the expansion of emerging economies like China and India. Peak oil theory suggests that, while prohibitively costly gasoline may not be on the horizon anytime soon, the days of cheap fuel, which lasted for over ten years following the collapse of OPEC cartel prices in the mid-1980s, are unlikely to come again.

The fact that the Nigerian economy is largely dependent on the oil sector—which, according to the World Bank, generates over 95% of export earnings and roughly 85% of government revenues—as well as the rapid depletion of global oil reserves are concerning. This article aims to forecast the imminence of Nigeria's diminishing oil reserves, the "unity probability" of its relative resource/reserve occurrence eventually being depleted, and the implications for its oil-dependent energy industry.

Nigeria is used as a case study due to its present success in diversifying into emerging renewable energy, which is a different energy source with a similar abundance of resources and other potential but underutilized energy sources, along with the severe economic difficulties associated with generating revenue from it. This strategy runs counter to the Hirsch study, which claims that "the U.S. and the world face an unprecedented risk management problem as a result of the peaking of world oil production." Liquid fuel prices and price volatility will skyrocket as peaking draws near, with enormous economic, social, and political ramifications if prompt mitigation is not taken. There are workable solutions for both supply and demand reduction, but in order to make a significant difference, they need to be started over ten years before the peak (Hirsch et al., 2007).

2.2.2. Resource Curse Theory

Countries with rich natural resources, such as oil, typically have slower rates of economic growth and worse development results than countries with fewer resources, according to the Resource Curse Theory, also known as the paradox of plenty. This idea suggests that oil-rich nations like Nigeria can experience detrimental economic outcomes like conflict, corruption, and bad governance. Because oil prices fluctuate and affect government revenues and economic planning, oil dependency can result in economic instability. Similar to this, resource richness may erode institutions by fostering corruption and decreasing accountability, impeding economic growth and the fight against poverty (Sachs & Warner, 2001).

2.2.3. Dutch Disease Theory

According to the Dutch Disease idea, a thriving oil industry may cause other economic sectors to contract. A country's native currency rises in response to a resource boom, like an oil discovery, which reduces the competitiveness of other exports and causes manufacturing and agriculture to decrease. The inflow of oil revenue causes the national currency to appreciate, hurting non-oil sectors and potentially increasing unemployment in those sectors. The neglect of other economic sectors due to an overemphasis on oil production can lead to long-term economic imbalances and increased poverty (Corden, & Neary, 1982).

2.2.4. Poverty Alleviation Models

The effectiveness of oil production in alleviating poverty depends on how oil revenues are utilized. This model suggests that benefits from economic growth, including those driven by oil production, eventually trickle down to all segments of society, including the poor. In practice, however, this model has been criticized for failing to address income inequality and for often benefiting the wealthy disproportionately. This theory focus on ensuring that growth directly benefits the poor through targeted social programs, employment creation, and equitable resource distribution. Effective poverty alleviation

requires policies that ensure oil revenues are allocated to social services, infrastructure development, and poverty reduction programs (Hirshman, 1958).

3. Methodology

3.1. Theoretical Framework

According to M. King Hubbert's 1956 Peak Oil Theory, also called Hubbert's Peak, oil output increases gradually until it reaches a peak, following a bell-shaped curve. Oil output will unavoidably fall after the peak, resulting in a permanent decline in oil production worldwide. When roughly half of all recoverable oil reserves have been depleted, the peak is reached. There will be an ongoing oil shortage as a result of the irreversible output drop.

3.2. Model Specification

The peak oil hypothesis, which was applied elsewhere by Simmons (2005), Heinberg (2003), and Deffeyes (2001), is the basis for the model modified for this study. It postulates that oil output follows a bell-shaped curve, peaking and then declining. In oil-dependent nations like Nigeria, this drop may have an effect on economic growth and the fight against poverty.

On the one hand, a single multivariate regression equation model uses oil production as the independent variable and economic development as the dependent variable to describe the proposed relationship between the two. However, a comparable multivariate regression model describes the relationship between poverty alleviation and oil production, with poverty alleviation in this instance being the dependent variable and oil production as the independent variable. The general forms of the models are described as follows:

$$PCI_t = \beta_1 OP_t + \beta_2 TAR_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 LER_t \quad (1)$$

$$POV_t = \beta_1 OP_t + \beta_2 LER_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 LR_t \quad (2)$$

Therefore, equation (1) can be re-written in an econometric form as:

$$PCI_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OP_t + \beta_2 TAR_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 LER_t + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

PCI = Per Capita Income

OP = Oil Production

TAR = Tariff rate

INF = Inflation Rate

LER = Life expectancy rate

β_0 = error term the intercept parameter

β_1 to β_5 = The slopes of the independent variables

μ = Random error term

Equation (2) can also be rewritten as follows in an econometric format:

$$POV_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OP_t + \beta_2 LER_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 LR_t + \mu_t \quad (4)$$

Where:

POV = Poverty rate

OP = Oil Production

LER = Life expectancy rate

INF = Inflation Rate

LR = Literacy rate

β_0 = the intercept parameter

β_1 to β_5 = The slopes of the independent variables

μ =Random error term

A-PRIORI EXPECTATION FOR MODEL 1:

It is expected that, economic development and oil production should be positively related. i.e $\beta_1 < 0$, Ceteris paribus. Furthermore, it is expected that, there should exist a negative relationship between the rate of tariff and economic development. Ceteris paribus therefore, $\beta_2 < 0$.

Also, it is expected that, the relationship between Inflation rate and economic development should be negative. Ceteris paribus therefore, $\beta_3 < 0$. Expectedly, there should be a direct relationship between life expectancy rate and economic development, ceteris paribus. Hence, the coefficient of population, $\beta_4 > 0$.

A-PRIORI EXPECTATION FOR MODEL 2:

Expectedly, there should exist an indirect relationship between poverty rate and oil production. An increased oil production is an indication of higher government revenue and subsequently more fiscal spending which will translate into poverty reduction through the multiplier effect ceteris paribus. Hence, $\beta_1 < 0$. Also, there should be a direct relationship between life expectancy rate and Poverty rate. The idea is that, a higher life expectancy rate means that people will now live longer and therefore earn more ceteris paribus. Hence, the coefficient of life expectancy $\beta_2 < 0$. In a normal economic sense, Inflation and poverty rate should be positively related. A general rise in price level increases poverty ceteris paribus. Hence $B_3 > 0$. Lastly, the relationship between poverty rate and literacy rate is expected to be negative. Hence, $B_4 < 0$

3.3. Estimation techniques

The Granger causality test was used to establish the flow of causation between the variables of the model, the ADF (Augmented Dickey Fuller) technique was used to test for the presence of a unit root in the data, and the ECM techniques were used to test for the existence of a long-term relationship between the variables of the model. The ARDL technique was chosen because time trend is a significant characteristic of time series data that typically results in non-stationarity issues. The Ordinary Least Square Estimation (OLS) technique will be used to examine the data if the results of the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test indicate that all of the series are stationary at level. The Engle Granger Co-integration test would be used to determine whether there is a long-term link between the I(1) series if the variables are not stationary at level, especially if the series are all I(1) series, or stationary at first difference. The ARDL co-integrating and long run form, a short run error correction technique that combines the short run and long run characteristics of the series, would be used if the bound test result showed that there was a long-term relationship. If the long-term relationship was not found, the I(0) s series would enter the ARDL model at its level, and the I(1) series would enter the model at first difference.

3.4. Data Measurement

Data is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Data presentation

Variables	Definition	Measurement	Source
PCI	Per capita income	Gross Domestic Product divided by population measured in Naira	WDI (2024)
POV	Poverty Rate	Percentage of people living below poverty line of \$2 per day	WDI (2024)
OP	Oil Production	Barrels of oil produced per year in US\$	CBN (2024)

TAR	Tariff	Tax imposed on imports measured in Naira	CBN (2024)
INF	Inflation Rate	Rate of increase in general price level	CBN (2024)
LER	Life expectancy rate	Number of years a person can expect to live	WDI (2024)
LR	Literacy rate	Number of people that has basic education	WDI (2024)

Source: Authors' Compilation (2024)

4. Analysis and Discussion of Findings

MODEL ONE

4.1.Descriptive statistics

Table 2. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	POV	INF	LER	LR	OP
Mean	-8.373030	18.25826	49.49976	8.894545	733.3712
Median	0.000000	12.38637	48.24000	0.000000	768.7459
Maximum	90.80000	72.8355	55.18000	70.20000	918.6606
Minimum	-94.00000	5.388008	45.45000	0.000000	277.4921
Std. Dev.	52.74812	16.89387	3.372549	21.54024	151.3259
Skewness	-0.034640	2.076106	0.359904	2.010479	-1.508092
Kurtosis	2.981474	6.157526	3.372549	5.173490	5.131916
Jarque-Bera	0.007072	34.01354	3.370507	28.72672	18.75834
Probability	0.996470	0.000000	0.185397	0.000001	0.000084
Sum	-276.3100	547.7478	1633.492	293.5200	24201.25
Sum Sq. Dev.	89035.65	8276.684	363.9708	14847.42	732784.7
Observations	33	33	33	33	33

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

The mean (average value of the variables over the period), the standard deviation (difference from the mean behavior), and the lowest and maximum values recorded during the period are among the results of the summary statistics that are shown in Table 2.

The findings indicate that the Poverty Rate (POV) has a mean of -8.373030, a standard deviation of 52.74812, a minimum of -94.00000, and a high of 90.80000. These show that the nation's average point of view over the study period was -8.373030, with a deviation of 52.74812 from this average behavior. During this time, the highest reported POV was 90.80000, and the lowest was -94.00000.

The inflation rate (INF) ranges from a low of 5.388008 to a maximum of 72.8355, with a mean of 18.25826, standard deviation of 16.89387. According to these, the average annual inflation rate was 18.25826 percent, with a deviation of 16.89387 percent from this average. During this time, the lowest reported inflation rate was 5.388008 percent, while the highest recorded rate was 72.8355 percent.

The Life Expectancy Rate (LER) ranges from a low of -2.035119 to a maximum of 18.61837, with a mean of 49.49976 and a standard deviation of 5.293515. According to this, the average yearly life expectancy over the study period was 49.49976, with a deviation of 5.293515 from this average behavior. Throughout the period, the lowest recorded LER value was 2.035119, and the highest recorded LER value was 18.61837.

The literacy rate (LR) ranges from a minimum of 0.000000 to a maximum of 70.20000, with a mean of 8.894545 and a standard deviation of 21.54024. These show an average literacy rate of 8.894545 percent for the study period, with a deviation of 21.54024 percent from this average behavior. During this time, the greatest documented literacy rate was 70.20000 percent, while the lowest was 0.000000 percent.

The mean of Oil Production (OP) is 733.3712, the standard deviation is 812.5847, the minimum is 277.4921, and the maximum is 918.6606. These show that the average amount of oil produced over the study period was 733.3712, with a deviation of 812.5847 from this average behavior. During this time, the lowest recorded OP value was 277.4921, and the highest recorded OP value was 918.6606.

4.2. Unit Root Test

Table 3. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Statistics	P-value	Order of integration
IR	-4.286837	0.0109***	I(1)
LER	-5.587113	0.0004***	I(1)
OP	-5.379998	0.0008***	I(1)
PCI	-4.582847	0.0049***	I(1)
TAR	-9.179008	0.0000***	I(0)

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

(***) denotes significance of the p-value at 5% level of significance

Only one of the entire series is stationary at level, and that is Tariff (TAR), which is integrated of order zero and is thus considered an I(0) series, according to the results of the ADF unit root test on the series, which are given in Table 3 above. All other variables, however, are considered I(1) series since they became stationary after calculating their initial difference. The outcome of the ADF test implies that it is necessary to ascertain whether a long-term relationship (co-integration) exists between the variables. Because the series are a combination of I(1) and I(0) series, the ARDL Bound Test will be used.

4.3. Co-integration Test

Table 4. ARDL Bound Test

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	0.364278	4
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

If the F-statistic is higher than the upper bound critical value (I1Bound) at a given level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and it is determined that the series are co-integrated. Because the F-statistic (0.364278) is less than the lower bound critical value at the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is not rejected in this case, and it is determined that the series are not co-integrated (table 4). The series' non-stationarity and non-cointegration imply that we can only examine the series' behavior or their relationship to one another within the time period (1990–2022) that is being studied; generalization to other time periods may not be feasible. Therefore, given the two aforementioned conditions, the most appropriate technique to use now for estimation is a First Difference ARDL model (table 5).

Table 5. First Difference ARDL Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
D(PCI(-1))	0.393223	0.150268	2.616814	0.0308
D(IR)	-15.27971	13.97730	-1.093180	0.3061
D(IR(-1))	-10.55022	13.43991	-0.784992	0.4551
D(LER)	326.8124	159.2005	2.052836	0.0742
D(LER(-1))	453.4246	175.2659	2.587067	0.0323
D(OP)	0.259520	0.424983	0.610660	0.5584
D(OP(-1))	0.162317	1.111614	0.146019	0.8875
D(TAR)	-1.265379	4.973289	-0.254435	0.8056
D(TAR(-1))	0.653435	8.367076	0.078096	0.9397
C	-1461.545	4616.946	-0.316561	0.7597
R-squared	0.925468	Mean dependent var		55.55542
Adjusted R-squared	0.739137	S.D. dependent var		378.7711
S.E. of regression	193.4565	Akaike info criterion		13.52840
Sum squared resid	299403.2	Schwarz criterion		14.51851
Log likelihood	-175.1619	Hannan-Quinn criter.		13.83849
F-statistic	4.966797	Durbin-Watson stat		2.436212
Prob(F-statistic)	0.012767			

Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Per capita income has a positive and significant impact on the model at the 0.05 level of significance, according to the above First Difference ARDL results, which show that the coefficient of per capita income D(PCI(-1)) in the prior year is positive at 0.393223 with an t-Statistic of 2.616814 and a probability value of 0.0308. This suggests that in order to explain how certain independent variables affect Nigeria's economic progress, per capita income (PCI) is an endogenous variable.

Inflation Rate (IFR): The coefficient of inflation rate (IFR) at first year is negative at -15.27971 and also negative in the previous year at -1.925644 with t-Statistic of -1.093180 and -0.784992 and probability value of 0.3061 and 0.4551 which means that inflation rate has negative effect on per capita income in Nigeria. However, the result delineates that both the past and the current values of Inflation rate are not significant at all levels since their respective P-values are all greater than 0.1 at 10% significance level.

The result also shows that there exists a direct relationship between the current value of life expectancy rate (LER) and per capita income (PCI). Given that, its coefficient is positive at 326.8124 with t-Statistic of 2.052836 and probability value of 0.0742. Therefore, the impact of life expectancy rate on per capital income is significant since its p-value (0.0742) is less than 0.1 at 10% significance level.

Conversely, the result delineates that both the past and the current values of Oil production and Tariff are not significant at all levels since their respective P-values are all greater than 0.1. i.e they have no significant impact on per capita income and economic growth.

4.4. Residual Diagnostic Tests

Table 6. Summary of Residual Test

	Test Statistic	P-value
Breusch-Godfrey (BG) Serial Correlation LM test	2.747046	0.1422
Breusch-Pagan Heteroscedasticity Test	0.708568	0.7484
Jacque Bera Normality test		0.0056

Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

From table 6 above, the P-value of the test statistic in the BG Serial Correlation test is greater than 0.05. Thus we can conclude that there is no serial correlation among the series in the model. Similarly, the Breusch-Pagan Heteroskedasticity test result posits that Heteroscedasticity is not present in the model, since the P-value of the test statistic is not significant at all levels. In other words, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there's no Heteroskedasticity in the model. Also, in the Jacque Bera test, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that the error terms of the series in the model are not normally distributed since the P-value of the test statistic is greater than 0.05.

4.5. Discussion and Implication of Results

It is clear from the foregoing description of the regression results that the historical value of oil production had no discernible effect on Nigeria's per capita income throughout the study's focus period (1990–2022). This indicates that, in spite of the enormous amount of oil produced in the past and the enormous profits generated by it, the industry has not substantially raised people's standard of living. The government's careless and inadequate handling of the sector's money may be partially to blame for this lack of effect. Despite Nigeria's heavy reliance on the oil industry, which has generated enormous wealth, the average Nigerian has not been able to benefit from the wealth due to corruption and poor management by the ruling class, whether through wasteful public investments or outright looting of the public treasury. This has led to an increase in inequality, poverty, unemployment, inflation, and the low standard of living in the country. Furthermore, other possible areas that could provide the government with income are completely ignored. Agriculture, which employs over 70% of the workforce and accounts for a larger share of the nation's GDP, has been completely disregarded.

MODEL TWO

4.6. Descriptive statistics

Table 7. Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	POV	INF	LER	LR	OP
Mean	-8.373030	18.25826	49.49976	8.894545	733.3712
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Minimum	-94.00000	5.388008	45.45000	0.000000	277.4921
Std. Dev.	52.74812	16.89387	3.372549	21.54024	151.3259
Skewness	-0.034640	2.076106	0.359904	2.010479	-1.508092
Kurtosis	2.981474	6.157526	3.372549	5.173490	5.131916
Jarque-Bera	0.007072	34.01354	3.370507	28.72672	18.75834
Probability	0.996470	0.000000	0.185397	0.000001	0.000084
Sum	-276.3100	547.7478	1633.492	293.5200	24201.25
Sum Sq. Dev.	89035.65	8276.684	363.9708	14847.42	732784.7
Observations	33	33	33	33	33

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

The mean (average value of the variables over the period), the standard deviation (difference from the mean behavior), and the lowest and maximum values recorded during the period are among the results of the summary statistics that are shown in Table 7.

The findings indicate that the Poverty Rate (POV) has a mean of -8.373030, a standard deviation of 52.74812, a minimum of -94.00000, and a high of 90.80000. This shows that the country's average POV during the study period was -8.373030, with a deviation of 52.74812 from this average behavior. During this time, the highest reported POV was 90.80000, and the lowest was -94.00000.

A mean of 18.25826, a standard deviation of 16.89387, a minimum of 5.388008, and a maximum of 72.8355 are displayed by the inflation rate (INF). These show that the yearly inflation rate was 18.25826 percent on average, with a deviation of 16.89387 percent from this average. Over the course of the time, the greatest recorded inflation rate was 72.8355 percent, while the lowest was 5.388008 percent.

Life Expectancy Rate (LER) has a mean value of 49.49976, standard deviation of 5.293515, -2.035119 at the minimum and 18.61837 at the maximum. According to this, the average yearly life expectancy over the study period was 49.49976, with a deviation of 5.293515 from this average behavior. Throughout the period, the lowest recorded LER value was 2.035119, and the highest recorded LER value was 18.61837.

The literacy rate (LR) ranges from a minimum of 0.000000 to a maximum of 70.20000, with a mean of 8.894545 and a standard deviation of 21.54024. These show an average literacy rate of 8.894545 percent for the study period, with a deviation of 21.54024 percent from this average behavior. During this time, the greatest documented literacy rate was 70.20000 percent, while the lowest was 0.000000 percent.

The mean of Oil Production (OP) is 733.3712, the standard deviation is 812.5847, the minimum is 277.4921, and the maximum is 918.6606. These show that the average amount of oil produced over the study period was 733.3712, with a deviation of 812.5847 from this average behavior. During this time, the lowest recorded OP value was 277.4921, and the highest recorded OP value was 918.6606.

4.7. Unit Root Test

Table 8. Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Variable	ADF Statistics	P-value	Order of integration
IFR	-9.646018	0.0000***	I(1)
LER	-5.587113	0.0004***	I(1)
LR	-6.483077	0.0000***	I(0)
OP	-5.379998	0.0008***	I(1)
UEM	-7.084016	0.0000***	I(0)

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

(***) denotes significance of the p-value at 5% level of significance

The results of the ADF unit root test on the series are reported in Table 8 above, which shows that two of the series were integrated of order 0 because they were stationary at level. Nevertheless, after calculating their initial difference, every variable proved to be stationary, and as a result, they are all considered I(1) series. The ARDL bound test is therefore the most appropriate for determining whether or not a long-term relationship exists among the variables because the variables are mixtures of both I(0) and I(1) series, according to the ADF test result.

4.8. Estimated Short Run Model

Table 9. Summary of ARDL Cointegration form results

ARDL Cointegrating And Long Run Form				
Dependent Variable: POV				
Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(POV(-1))	0.504057	0.140404	3.590054	0.0042
D(IFR)	-2.438515	0.689832	-3.534940	0.0047
D(IFR(-1))	2.065087	0.629625	3.279868	0.0073
D(LER)	9.440191	13.861375	0.681043	0.5099
D(OP)	-0.071067	0.065130	-1.091145	0.2985
D(OP(-1))	0.162711	0.075626	2.151525	0.0545
D(OP(-2))	-0.060419	0.068313	-0.884453	0.3954
D(OP(-3))	-0.351676	0.077527	-4.536199	0.0008
D(LR)	0.268299	0.332602	0.806666	0.4370
D(LR(-1))	0.636089	0.337806	1.883003	0.0864
D(LR(-2))	-0.392198	0.304875	-1.286420	0.2247
D(LR(-3))	-1.933400	0.351143	-5.506013	0.0002
CointEq(-1)	-2.314649	0.249344	-9.282969	0.0000
Cointeq = POV - (-1.2442*IFR - 3.2542*LER - 0.0222*OP + 0.2124*LR + 185.3125)				

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

The coefficient of CointEq (-1) represents the Error Correction Model (ECM) term, which must be negative and significant, as shown in table 9 above. This is the pace of transitioning from short-term to long-term equilibrium. In addition to being statistically significant, the one period lag error correction term CointEq (-1) is negative and less than one. It is implied that there is a rapid rate of transition from the short to the long term. Adjusting back from the short run to the long runs takes an average of 231% if there is any disequilibrium in the variables.

According to the short-term model results, the coefficient of inflation rate D (INF) is negative at - 2.438515, meaning that a 2% increase in the current year's inflation rate lowers the poverty level by 2.438515 percent. At the 5% significance level, this effect is statistically significant because the corresponding p-value of 0.0047 is less than 0.05.

The coefficient of D(INF(-1)) is positive at 2.065087. This implies that a percentage increase in Inflation rate with one year lag (in the last year) increases the poverty rate by 2.065087percent. This effect is statistically significant at 5% significance level as the associated p-value is less than 0.05.

The coefficient of oil production D(OP) is about -0.071067 which implies that a unit increase in oil production in the current year will decrease poverty rate by 0.071067 percent and its probability value of 0.2985 shows this to be statistically insignificant at all level of significance.

Life expectancy rate, D(LER) has a positive coefficient of 9.440191 which implies a positive relationship between the LER in the current year and poverty rate. But this result is not statistically significant as its p-value (0.5099) is greater at 10% level of significance

Additionally, the likelihood value indicates that the literacy rate (LR) coefficient is positive but not statistically significant.

4.9. Estimated Long Run Model

Table 10. Summary of ARDL Long Run Coefficients

Dependent Variable: POV				
Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
IFR	-1.244228	0.313857	-3.964309	0.0022

LER	-3.254233	1.593695	-2.041942	0.0659
OP	-0.022169	0.034162	-0.648937	0.5297
LR	0.212393	0.274518	0.773695	0.4554
C	185.312518	101.197829	1.831191	0.0943

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

The above ARDL long run form result shows that in the long run, only Inflation rate (INF) and Life expectancy (LER) are significant at 5% and 10% significant level respectively. However, Oil production (OP) and Literacy rate are not statistically significant as revealed by their respective probability values.

From the table 10, OP has a coefficient of about -0.022169 which implies that a unit increase in oil production in the long run, decreases poverty level by about 0.022169 percent. OP probability value of 0.5297 which is greater than 5% and 10% further explains that in the long run, Oil production does not have a significant impact on Poverty rate.

Similarly, Literacy rate (LR) has no significant impact on poverty level in the long run as revealed by its probability value of 0.4554 which is greater than 5% and 10% significance levels.

Conversely, Inflation rate (INF) has a coefficient of about -1.244228 which implies that a percentage increase in inflation rate in the long run, decreases Poverty rate by about 1.244228 percent. INF probability value of 0.0022 which is less than 5% further explains that in the long run, Inflation rate have a significant impact on Poverty level.

Similarly, Life expectancy rate (LER) has a coefficient of about -3.254233 which implies that a percentage increase in Life expectancy in the long run, decreases Poverty rate by about 3.254233 percent. LER probability value of 0.0659 which is less than 10% further explains that in the long run, Inflation rate have a significant impact on Poverty level.

4.10. Residual Diagnostic Tests

Table 11. Summary of Residual Test

	Test Statistic	P-value
Breusch-Godfrey (BG) Serial Correlation LM test	2.736362	0.1179
Breusch-Pagan Heteroscedasticity Test	3.096181	0.0308
Jacque Bera Normality test	0.093406	0.954371

Source: Authors' Computation Using Eviews 9 (2024)

The BG Serial Correlation test's P-value is greater than 0.05, as seen in the table 11. As a result, we may say that the series in the model do not serially correlate. Similarly, because the P-value of the test statistic is not significant at any levels, the Breusch-Pagan Heteroskedasticity test result suggests that heteroscedasticity is absent from the model. Stated otherwise, we are unable to reject the null hypothesis and come to the conclusion that the model does not exhibit heteroskedasticity. Additionally, because the P-value of the test statistic is higher than 0.05, we are unable to reject the null hypothesis in the Jacque Bera test and come to the conclusion that the error terms of the series in the model are normally distributed. Therefore, the classical normality assumption of the classical linear regression model is not violated.

5. Discussion and Implication of Results

From the empirical regression results above it can be inferred that, within the period under consideration in this study (1990 to 2022), Inflation rate have significant impact on Poverty rate in Nigeria. This attributed to rising inflation in recent years. Constant increase in the prices of goods and services, high cost of transportation, high lending rate are some of the resultant effects of inflation ravaging the Nigerian economy.

Nigeria's inflation rate rose to 33.2% in March 2024, according to Nairametrics. Compared to the 31.7% recorded in February 2024, this indicates a 1.5% increase. Additionally, the food inflation rate increased

by 15.56% points from 24.45% in March 2023 to 40.01% year over year. In addition, during the previous year, the average cost of housing, water, electricity, gas, and other fuels increased by 27.64%. These factors make it very evident that inflation is still a major threat to Nigerians' standard of living, driving up living expenses and ultimately putting millions of them in poverty.

However, the results show that oil production doesn't have any significant impact on poverty alleviation. This lack of impact may, to an extent, be blamed upon the government's poor and reckless management of revenue coming from the sector. Nigeria has made substantive amount of money from oil. However, the rate of poverty keeps going up despite the huge sum of money. This could be blamed on the leaders' inability to use the revenue generated in the oil sector to finance projects that will give the economy a massive turnaround and aid poverty reduction.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1. Conclusion

The findings from the study depicts that, Oil Production (OR) in the current and past period is not significant at all levels since its respective P-values is greater than 0.1. Hence, it did not significantly impact economic development and poverty alleviation. Thus, we can conclude that Oil revenue from 1990 to 2022 did not significantly improve economic development and poverty alleviation in Nigeria.

6.2. Recommendations

The following suggestions are made to the government in light of the study's findings.

The findings demonstrate that neither Nigeria's economic development nor its attempts to combat poverty were significantly impacted by oil output. To ensure that oil production and its profits are successful in fostering economic growth and reducing poverty, government money must be allocated and directed into productive and efficient programs and initiatives. It is equally important to invest in the physical and social infrastructure required to promote long-term prosperity and the reduction of poverty.

In order to ensure that the oil industry is run accurately and effectively, the awarding of oil blocks, contracts, permits, and production rights should also adhere to due process without interference from the government or its representatives. Additionally, corporate businesses with wide ownership should be given preference over private individuals when it comes to assigning oil blocks.

Furthermore, efforts should be geared by the Nigerian state towards reducing dependence on the petroleum sector, through diversification of the economy. In addition to these, there is need for government to improve the living conditions of the people with the oil wealth through the provision of basic social amenities such as electricity, good roads, employment, good health care system, pipe borne water to mention a few.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

References

1. Adeola, F., & Evans, O. (2019). Oil and economic growth in Nigeria: The role of governance. *Journal of African Business*, 20(1), 59-78.
2. Akpoyomare, A. O. (2016). Environmental impacts of oil exploration and production in the Niger Delta. *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part C*, 34(1), 53-67.
3. Baumeister, C., & Kilian, L. (2016). Forty Years of Oil Price Fluctuations: Why the Price of Oil May Still Surprise Us. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. 30(1), 139-160.
4. Bolarinwa, T. A. (2023). Effect of formal education on poverty reduction in Nigeria. *Management of Sustainable Development Journal*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2023-0018>

5. Bucur, L.-M. (2023). Sustainable development: A viable solution to reduce poverty. *Management of Sustainable Development Journal*, 15(2). <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2023-0012>
6. CBN Statistical Bulletin 2021 (Federal Government Finances)
7. Central Bank of Nigeria. (2020). Annual Report.
8. Corden, W. M., & Neary, J. P. (1982). Booming sector and de-industrialization in a small open economy. *Economic Journal*, 92(368), 825-848. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2232675>
9. Deffeyes, K. S. (2001). *Hubbert's peak: The impending world oil shortage*. Princeton University Press.
10. Heinberg, R. (2003). *The party's over: Oil, war, and the fate of industrial societies*. New Society Publishers.
11. Hirshman, A. O. (1958). *The strategy of economic development*. Yale University Press.
12. Hirsch, R., Bezdek, R., & Wendling, R. (2007). Peaking of world oil production: Impacts, mitigation, and risk management. *Journal of Petroleum Technology*, 59(5), 62-71.
13. Human Rights Watch. (2021). *Nigeria: Oil and the Politics of Corruption*. Retrieved from Human Rights Watch
14. Ibeanu, O. (2020). The oil curse: Governance, economic development, and conflict in Nigeria. *African Security Review*, 29(3), 222-240.
15. Ighosewe, E. F., Akan, D. C., & Agbogun, O. E. (2021). Crude Oil Price Dwindling and the Nigerian Economy: A Resource-Dependence Approach. *Modern Economy*, 12, 1160-1184. <https://doi.org/10.4236/me.2021.127061>.
16. International Trade Administration. (2023). *Nigeria country commercial guide*. U.S. Department of Commerce. <https://www.trade.gov/nigeria-country-commercial-guide>
17. Iwayemi, A. (2014). Oil price shocks and macroeconomic performance in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 41(2), 240-253.
18. Iwayemi, A., Adenikinju, A., & Folarin, O. (2019). Oil Exploration and Exploitation in Nigeria and the Challenges of Sustainable Development in the Niger Delta Region. *Journal of Sustainable Development Law and Policy*, 10, 1-20.
19. National Bureau of Statistics. (2020). Poverty and inequality in Nigeria.
20. Ocolisanu, A., Dobrota, G., & Agarbiceanu, M. S. (2022). The implications of the circular economy on sustainable economic growth. *Management of Sustainable Development Journal*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.54989/msd-2022-0003>
21. Olofinbiyi, S., Ojeka, S., & Olawale, L. (2021). Economic effects of oil price fluctuations on Nigeria. *Energy Reports*, 7, 1265–1275.
22. OPEC. (2022). *Nigeria's oil production and economic performance*. Retrieved from OPEC
23. Ross, M. L. (2015). *The oil curse: How petroleum wealth shapes the development of nations*. Princeton University Press.
24. Sachs, J. D., & Warner, A. M. (2001). The curse of natural resources. *European Economic Review*, 45(4-6), 827-838. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921\(01\)00125-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0014-2921(01)00125-8).
25. Sasu, D. D. (2023). Nigeria: Contribution of Oil Sector to GDP. *Scientific Research Publishing Inc.*, 91(2), 198-201.
26. Simmons, M. R. (2005). *Twilight in the desert: The coming Saudi oil shock and the world economy*. Wiley.
27. UNDP. (2022). *Nigeria: Human Development Report*. Retrieved from UNDP
28. World Bank. (2022). World Development Indicators.

29. World Bank. (2023). *Nigeria economic update: Oil revenues and poverty*. Retrieved from World Bank

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